

PROCESS ANALYSIS OF HAND LAY UP METHOD BY VARIOUS EXPERIENCE PERSONS

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1 Introduction

Hand lay-up (HLU) method is used as one of the forming techniques of a fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) for many years. This is because HLU method only requires raw material, mold and human skill, also it can respond to change of quantity of the product or a size widely. Therefore the skill of those who fabricate influences the quality of a product greatly. For this reason, such as FRP fabrication proficiency measurement are used and instruction to a beginner is advancing. However, it is not clarified until now about a craftsman's skill which is called "TAKUMI" of hand lay-up skill. Moreover, it is not clarified about the relation between a craftsman's level of skill and quality of the product, which means mechanical properties and dimensional stability, etc.

On the other hand, if a strengthening base material, a strengthening form, base material resin, and volume content are the same, no matter what forming method it may use, it is thought that the characteristic of the composite becomes the same. The essence of FRP fabrication is replacing the air which makes resin impregnate with a fiber and which in other words is contained in the fiber by resin. Resin is made to impregnate with a strengthening fiber by using a roller in HLU method. Therefore, it is suggested that the methods of

impregnation has the possibilities to produce change of interfacial quality. In this study, in order to consider the influence of the roller in the HLU method to the mechanical property of a composite material, the FRP specimen was produced by various experience persons. The strength test of a specimen and observation of dimensional stability which were obtained by the process analysis were performed, and the analysis of a craftsman's level of skill and the relation of mechanical properties were taken place.

Moreover, in the process analysis, the number of times of a roller and a direction were mainly observed. And analysis of relationship between molding process and mechanical properties (Static strength and dynamic strength) were considered.

2 Measuring method

2.1 Subjects

In this study, 11 persons (having various experience years in HLU method) were targeted. Biological data of subjects are shown in table 1. Each subject has various years of experience (range from inexperience to 25 years in HLU method). In this study, manufacturing method is not taught to the subject in advance. Each subject manufactures by the original method. However, each subject is able to see freely the sample plate manufactured in advance. And tool to be used is not restricted in this

research. All subjects were right-handed person, and didn't have trouble with physical handicaps or medical disease that restrict work. The purpose and method of this study were explained in advance to subjects. And the consent to participation was obtained.

Table 1. Biological data of subjects.

Subject No.	Age	Years of experience	Male or Female	Dominant-hand
1	22	0.5	Male	Right
2	39	5	Male	Right
3	29	0	Male	Right
4	45	0	Male	Right
5	32	0	Male	Right
6	42	0	Male	Right
7	29	3	Male	Right
8	30	2	Male	Right
9	33	10	Male	Right
10	54	25	Male	Right
11	31	0	Male	Right

3.2 Analysis object

Analysis object was work which fabricated FRP flat plate by hand lay up method. In this study, mold is a metal smooth plate. The size of flat plate was as follows. 300 mm in length, 300 mm in width (Fig.1) .

Molding operation is laminating four glass cloths using roller. All the directions of warp of glass cloth are laminated in the same direction. Here, the direction of warp is defined as 0 degree, and the direction of the woof is defined as 90 degrees (Fig.1) .

It is pressing down with the laminated paper at the end of work so that there is no variation in the

thickness between subjects. There is cure time of 24 hours at 25°C after the end of work. Furthermore, there is after-cure time of 2 hours at 100°C. And the weight of 40 kg is applied at the time of hardening.

Fig.1. Mold for this study.

Fig.2. Laminated constitution.

Moreover, each subject's working times were also measured. Each subject fabricated only one FRP flat plate. The essence of composite material fabrication is replacing the air in a fiber by resin. And although various molding methods exist as a substitution method of this air and resin, a roller mainly carries out this duty in HLU method.

3.3 Atmosphere of measurement

Experiment was performed under the same work atmosphere as the usual workplace so that subjects could work usually. Moreover, instructions except restrictions of measurement were omitted so that subjects could work at one's own pace.

Motion analysis was done from start to finish of all the work process by using two video cameras (Fig.3). One of two video cameras records subject's motion from above (Fig.4), and the number of times of subject's roller and the place are able to be analyzed.

Fig.3 Motion analysis system in this experiment

Fig.4. Motion analysis (from above).

3.4 Material

As a base material, glass cloth (570g/m²) were used. And as a resin, unsaturated polyester resin (RIGOLAC150HRBQTNW) was used. Polymer was mixed with the hardener MEKPO in a ratio of 100:1.0. Moreover, in this study, the tool for lamination was not specified. The amount of resin in particular used in this study is not specified.

Fig.5.Glass cloth under impregnation.

3.5 Specimen

After fiber is laminated, FRP specimen is cut to do each mechanical test as fig.6. Each mechanical test is tensile test, fatigue test, bending test, cross sectional observation, crack growth observation by replica method. The number of each specimen of mechanical test is three things.

Moreover, in particular the edge part and cutting plane of a specimen are not carrying out polish etc. The form of specimen is as being shown in Fig.7.

Here, "Fatigue" is a phenomenon in which the intensity as a machine material of the object falls when an object receives mechanical stress continuously repeatedly. Fatigue occurs when a material is subjected to repeated loading and unloading. If the loads are above a certain threshold, microscopic cracks will begin to form at the stress concentrators such as the surface, persistent slip bands (PSBs), and grain interfaces. Eventually a crack will reach a critical size, and the structure will suddenly fracture. The shape of the structure will significantly affect the fatigue life; square holes or sharp corners will lead to elevated local stresses where fatigue cracks can initiate. Round holes and

smooth transitions or fillets are therefore important to increase the fatigue strength of the structure.

Fig. 6 Sampling of specimens for various tests.

Fig. 7. Specimens for tensile testing.

Strain gage and Acoustic Emission (AE) sensor are attached to the middle of a specimen. Here, in order to investigate the destructive progress by crack sound, AE sensor is used. The threshold is 25 dB.

Each subject's tensile test was done a total of 3 times.

Fig. 8. Acoustic Emission sensor system.

3.6 Process analysis

After roller behavior is filmed, the direction and number of subject's roller and the place are analyzed. The direction of subject's roller is selected for lengthwise, crosswise and diagonal. The number of subject's roller is counted at one time when roller is passed on a point of view is set at that center of specimen is used by tensile test. The number of subject's roller is expressed as the total of four ply.

Fig. 9 Definition of subject's roller

3.7 Mechanical properties

Tensile test is conducted by universal tester (INSTRON Type 4466). Tensile test condition is conformed by JIS K 7161. Tensile test speed is 1mm/min.

It is decided that Definition of knee point is section that graph is curved on stress-strain curve. It is thought that crack grow and strength is decreased on knee-point. Elastic modulus is a measure of the stiffness of an elastic material and is a quantity used to characterize materials. It is defined as the ratio of the stress along an axis over the strain along that axis in the range of stress in which Hooke's law holds. In solid mechanics, the slope of the stress-strain curve at any point is called the tangent modulus. The tangent modulus of the initial, linear portion of a stress-strain curve is called *Young's modulus*. It can be experimentally determined from the slope of a stress-strain curve created during tensile tests conducted on a sample of the material.

Fatigue test is conducted by hydraulic fatigue test machine. In order to mean what cyclic stress material can bear and by what stress it will fracture

if what number of times is given, the S-N curve (S-N curve) is used widely.

A S-N curve is a graph denoted by the logarithm of the number of times of a repetition (Number of cycles) until it repeats the stress on a vertical axis and loads and fractures it on it at stress amplitude (Stress amplitude) or a stress range (Stress range), and a horizontal axis. It is decide that Mean load of Fatigue test 5000N because knee point of Stress-strain curve .

Cross sectional observation is conducted by micro scope after FRP specimen is cut and polished.

3.8 Replica method

Fig.10 shows replica method. Crack growth observation is conducted by replica method. This is because large ply separation is happened in the specimen and it is difficult to observation by microscope when test specimen is pulled. Leplica method is the observation method that methyl acetate is put on crack in the side of specimen and acetylcellulose is pressed on the side of specimen when specimen is pulled. Then acetylcellulose is dissolved and crack in the specimen is copied on the acetylcellulose. After that, crack on the acetylcellulose is observed by microscope. By this method, crack growth can be observed when load is increased.

Fig.10 replica method

4 Results and consideration

4.1 Process analysis

First, the working times between each subject are compared (Table 2). Here, in each subject, each working times from 1st ply to 4th ply are compared.

If it compares in work sum total time, it can divide roughly into two groups. It is about whether it is less than 10 minutes. The subject who was less than 10 minutes was conscious of working times. However, other subjects are not conscious of working times in particular. The number of lengthwise subject's roller is most. And the number of Diagonal subject's roller is least for all subjects.

This graph shows 2 type of subject that the number of lengthwise roller more than the number of crosswise roller or the number of lengthwise and crosswise is almost same.

Table2 : Working-times comparison between subjects

Subject No.	1 st ply	2 nd ply	3 rd ply	4 th ply	total
1	5'52"	5'57"	5'27"	5'05"	22'21"
2	7'23"	3'08"	4'29"	14'56"	29'56"
3	7'08"	6'11"	7'17"	6'56"	27'32"
4	5'28"	6'01"	4'20"	6'31"	22'20"
5	5'47"	3'46"	4'48"	7'52"	22'13"
6	7'22"	7'52"	8'28"	7'15"	30'57"
7	2'34"	2'25"	3'10"	2'21"	10'30"
8	1'40"	1'41"	2'46"	3'08"	9'15"
9	1'34"	1'23"	1'21"	1'15"	5'33"
10	2'09"	1'32"	0'39"	2'14"	6'34"
11	1'34"	2'19"	2'12"	2'16"	8'21"

Fig.11 The number of roller action

4.2 Static strength

Result of mechanical property is shown in Table 2.

Table2 Mechanical property

Subject NO	Tensile strength [MPa]	Elastic modulus [GPa]
1	505	34.7
2	494	32.6
3	492	34.2
4	501	33.3
5	475	32.3
6	476	34.2
7	392	29.8
8	503	34.9
9	445	30.5
10	411	26.8
11	375	25.6

Tensile strength and elastic modulus are shown. Evaluation was performed to all three specimens. Mechanical property shown in Table 2 is mean for three specimen. Fig.12 is show graphically for Table 2. Among subjects, 44% of difference has arisen in tensile strength. And 46 % of difference has arisen in elastic modulus. Next, Stress-Strain curve is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig.12.Mechanical property.

Fig.13 Stress-Strain curve.

The dashed line in Fig.6 expresses AE counts. The standup of AE counts is the same among subjects. That is, it is thought that knee point of Stress-Strain curve is the same among subjects. However, there are many AE Counts in subject No.2. This is considered because the adhesive strength of the interface of fiber and resin is powerful as compared with other subjects. As a result, it is thought that tensile strength is also high.

Next, fracture cross section of some specimens is shown in Fig7. All subject's specimens after tensile strength testing remain as Fig.14, without fracturing fiber complete.

This is conjectured that interlayer peeling has occurred in the whole layer.

Fig14. Specimens after tensile testing.

4.3 Interface strength (Knee-point)

It is thought that knee point is influenced by inter face of fiber and resin. But knee point is not correlated with the number of lengthwise subject's roller.

Table3 Rank of strength at knee point

Rank	subject	Knee point (MPa)
1	subject 3	115
2	subject 4	107
3	subject 6	104
4	subject 1	98
5	subject 5	94
6	subject 8	90
7	subject 2	88
8	subject 7	82
9	subject 10	70
10	subject 11	67
11	subject 9	63

4.4 Dynamic strength

A fatigue design is based on repeated stress in many cases, and in order to ask for the stress which is equal to fatigue, the S-N (Strain - Number of cycle) diagram which plotted the rupture life (fracture number of cycle) of the material by repetition of constant strain is shown in Fig. 15. High-cycle fatigue testing is carried out. Mean load is 5,000N. Fatigue strength is not involved with tensile strength. Difference of fatigue strength is influenced by interface of fiber and resin.

Fig.15 Fatigue strength

4.5 Surface observation

This figure show surface observation by microscope. White section is void and shortage of impregnation. Tensile strength is influenced by the number of defect. The defect will be measured as void content.

Fig.16 Surface observation.

5 Conclusion

- 44% of difference has arisen in tensile strength.
- 46 % of difference has arisen in elastic modulus.
- Fatigue strength is not correlated with tensile strength.
- the number of lengthwise is most for all subjects

It is thought that tensile strength and elastic modulus is influenced by void or shortage of impregnation . Even if it used a strengthening base material, a strengthening form, base material resin, volume content, and the same forming technique from the above-mentioned result, it was suggested that FRP shows the different characteristic.

Therefore, the method of fabrication of the HLU method has had big influence on mechanical properties.

Furthermore, it was suggested that mechanical properties are also closely related to how to use the roller (directivity, number of times, load, etc.) which is a measure of a level of skill.

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